

**HANDBALL EFFICIENCY IN THE SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL
EDUCATION**

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Annotation: This article refers to classes on the developed program with the predominant use of handball tools applied at the Department of Physical Education in higher educational institutions and expanding the possibilities of improving the process of physical education of students. One of the forms of classes in this process is also provided for educational practice, during which a study was conducted to improve the quality of teaching “Physical Culture” based on the development and implementation of the Gandbol course for classes in a non-violent university.

Key words: Physical culture, handball, education system, efficiency.

Sports games can be confidently called a universal means of physical education of all category of the population from preschool children to pensioners. With their help, the goal is to form the formation of the foundations of the physical and spiritual culture of the personality. The role of sports games is great in solving the problems of physical education in a wide age range, such as the formation of a conscious need for the development of health values, physical culture and sports; physical improvement and

strengthening of health as a conditions for ensuring and achieving a high level of professionalism in socially significant types of activities; natural and individually acceptable development of physical potential, ensuring the achievement of the necessary and sufficient level of physical qualities, system of motor skills; physical education general education aimed at mastering the intellectual, technological, moral and aesthetic values of physical culture; Actualization of knowledge at the level of skills in conducting independent classes and skills to introduce others to them [1].

The inclusion of handball in the physical education program for a comprehensive school is not accidental. For this right, handball fought for a long time and won it deservedly and fairly. Back in 1898, the Lecturer of the Danish City of the Danish city of the Ordrupe Holger Nielsen introduced a game called “Haandbold” in his lessons, in which teams of 7 people competed in a small field, an advanced ball to each other and, trying to abandon it into the goal.

Like most sports games, the new game with throwing the ball liked the new one; Teams began to be created. So for the first time she appeared in the cities of Kharkov and Lviv in 1909. At first it was used in gymnastics lessons, and at the suggestion of Dr. E. Maly Gandbol was used in Kharkov gymnasiums as a means of physical education of the young generation. Former gymnasium students, going into the category of adults, continued to play handball [2].

The effectiveness of handball in the promotion of the harmonious development of the personality is explained, firstly, its specificity, and secondly, a deep versatile effect on the body of the development of physical qualities and the development of vital motor skills; Thirdly, the accessibility for people of various ages and preparedness (the level of physical activity is regulated in a wide range - from the insignificant in classes with a healing orientation to the maximum physical and mental stress at the level of sports of the highest achievements); Fourth, an emotional charge, here on this basis everyone is equal - “both old and young”; Fifth, sports games are a unique sight, on this basis other sports cannot be compared with them. The motor activity of handball players to the game is not just the sum of individual methods of defense and attack, but

a set of actions united by a common goal into a single dynamic system. The success of motor actions depends on the stability and variability of skills, the level of development of the physical qualities and intelligence of the players. Along with the most ancient disciplines of athletics, handball as a system of movements consists of the most natural motor actions based on the basis of running, jumping and throwing historically the most ancient movements of a person. This explains the harmonious influence of handball classes on the physical development of the body, this also determines the healing orientation of the game. The educational process consists of lectures and practical classes. One of the forms of classes in this process also provides for the educational practice, which conducted a study to improve the quality of teaching “Physical Culture” based on the development and introduction of the Gandbol course in the educational process for classes in a non -physical education university.

The results of the study showed that the targeted pedagogical influences implemented during the experimental verification of the developed program of the Gandbol course provides an increase to the identified values:

- interests of students in physical education and sports activities (45.0%), in particular to beach handball (93.7%);
- the level of knowledge in the field of pedagogical control of their physical fitness (31.7%);
- physical development (5.5%);
- functional indicators (13.0%) and physical condition (17.8%);
- attendance of training sessions (in the experimental group of passes for the disrespectful reason, it was not revealed).

The results of the experiment are given to recommend classes under the developed program with the predominant use of handball tools for use at the Department of Physical Education in higher educational institutions and expand the possibilities of improving the process of physical education of students. The lectures report about the essence and significance of the sport at the present stage, data on the history of the emergence and development of handballs, information on the preparation of young

athletes is given, the basics of the technique and tactics of the game are characterized, and the methodology of primary learning handballs is revealed.

In practical classes, students master the technique and tactics of handball, improve physical and technical tactical preparedness, master the necessary professional and pedagogical knowledge, skills and improve them.

At the stage of basic learning, discipline consists of the following sections:

1. General issues of the theory and methods of gaming sports ("Sports Game", "Handball Technique", "Handball Tactics", "Training", "Training", "Training", etc.).
2. Fundamentals of the theory and technique of handball (characteristic and essence of the game, history of the occurrence, development trends, features of the physique of handballers and motor abilities, the development of special physical qualities, game and competitive activity, technique and tactics (training), rules and refereeing of competitions and judges of competitions and competitions of competitions and etc.).

This electronic textbook provides information about such a sport as handball, which is included in the program of the Olympic Games. It has many valuable information on issues such as the history of the appearance and development of handball, the rules of the game, judicial gestures, the general characteristics of the movements, the size of the field, etc. The textbook is also equipped with a glossary, a hundred training video surveys, pictures and schemes, tests for self -assessment of knowledge. Functional capabilities of the program: quick access to the desired section, material and topic; View many pages of the studied text in a fraction of a second; the use of multimedia capabilities, which allows you to make the subject being studied more interesting and understandable; Providing the student with the opportunity to independently perform tasks (oral surveys, tests, etc.).

In the conclusion of the analysis of this article, it becomes clear that the pedagogical technology for Handball is used in many educational institutions of higher education, while at the same time, such a distribution of sports games found its

reflection in the studied literary sources as an independent means of physical improvement of students of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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